

Supplemental Figures

Suppl. Figure 1. FGF401 inhibited FGFR4 phosphorylation in vitro on NHLF.

Dot plot with median showing phospho-FGFR4 expression measured by ELISA in NHLF (n=3) after treatment with FGF401 (10nM) for 5min as compared to basal condition.

Suppl. Figure 2. *FGFR4* mRNA is negatively correlated with extra-cellular matrix genes expression

Heat map of 200 genes ranked by Spearman correlation coefficient the COL score and the normalized expression of the gene of interest in myofibroblast. 200 genes were selected based on a significant highest and lowest correlation coefficient with the COL score. Significant correlation was defined as adjusted p-value (FDR) <0.05. Each column represents the z-score normalized gene expression for single cell, hierarchically grouped by disease status and COL score. Z-score values are from -2 to 2 across rows within each categorical cell.

Suppl. Figure 3. Characterization of lung phenotype in *Fgfr4* deficient mice compared to wild type littermates at baseline at 8 weeks.

(A) Representative Hematoxylin and eosin staining of lung tissue sections from naive *Fgfr4*^{-/-} mice (n=5) or wild type (WT) littermates (n=5) (B) Dot plots with median showing mRNA lung expression of *Collagen 1a1* (*Colla*), *Fibronectin* (*Fn1*) and *Acta2* in *Fgfr4*^{-/-} mice and littermates. (C) Dot plots with medians showing lung collagen content (µg/lobe) in *Fgfr4*^{-/-} mice and WT littermates. Scale bar: 1000 µm in low magnification images (A). Mann Whitney U test was performed.

Suppl. Figure 4. Confirmation of *Fgfr4* loss in *Fgfr4* deficient mice receiving bleomycin.

Dot plots with median showing mRNA lung expression of *Fgfr4* in *Fgfr4*^{-/-} mice (n=9) and littermates (n=18) injected with saline or bleomycin. Mann Withney U test ***p≤0.001.

Suppl. Figure 1.

Suppl. Figure 2.

Suppl. Figure 3.

A

B

B

Supplemental Table 1 : PCR primer sequences

Gene	Forward	Reverse
<i>mRna18S</i>	CTTAGAGGGACAAGTGGCG	ACGCTGAGCCAGTCAGTGTA
<i>mActa2</i>	AGTCGCTGTCAGGAACCCTGAGA	ATTGTGCGCACACCAGGGCTGTG
<i>mCol1a1</i>	GTGTGTGACAAGGGTGAGACA	GAGAACCAGGAGAACCAGGA
<i>mFn1</i>	TGGTGGCCACTAAATACGAA	GGAGGGCTAACATTCTCCAG

Taqman probes

<i>hUBC</i>	Hs00824723
<i>hFGFR4</i>	Hs01106910
<i>mRna18S</i>	Mm03928990
<i>mFgfr4</i>	Mm01341852

(Thermo Fisher, Waltham, États-Unis).

Supplementary Table 2: Antibodies list

Antibody	Dilution	Reference	Application
FGFR4	1/1000	Rabbit monoclonal, Abcam, Cambridge, USA (ab5481)	Western Blot
GAPDH	1/10000	Mouse monoclonal, Covalab, Villeurbanne, France (00006513)	Western Blot
β -TUBULIN	1/2500	Rabbit polyclonal, Abcam, Cambridge, USA (ab6046)	Western Blot
β -ACTIN	1/2000	Mouse monoclonal clone AC-74 (A2228), Sigma, Saint-Louis, USA	Western Blot
COL-I	1/1000	Goat polyclonal, Southern Biotech, Birmingham, USA (1310-01)	Western Blot
FN-1	1/2000	Rabbit polyclonal, Abcam, Cambridge, UK (ab2413)	Western Blot
ACTA2	1/1000	Mouse monoclonal, clone 1A4, Sigma, Saint-Louis, USA (A5228)	Western Blot
JNK	1/1000	Rabbit monoclonal, Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, USA (#9252)	Western Blot
Phospho-JNK	1/1000	Rabbit monoclonal, Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, USA (#4668)	Western Blot
HSC70	1/1000	Mouse monoclonal, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, USA (sc-7298)	Western Blot

Secondary antibodies

Antibody	Dilution	Reference	Application
Anti-rabbit IgG, HRP-linked	1/10000	Goat, Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, USA (#7074)	Western Blot
Anti-mouse IgG, HRP-linked	1/10000	Horse, Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, USA (#7076)	Western Blot
Anti-Goat IgG HRP-linked	1/5000	Donkey, Jackson ImmunoResearch Europe Ltd, Cambridge, UK (705-035-147)	Western Blot